

VIEWS ON SPEECH CULTURE AND SPEECH IN ALISHER NAVOI'S “NAZM UL-JAVOKHIR”

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6492566>

Abstract: This article describes Alisher Navoi's views on oratory, speech culture and speech in “Nazm ul-javokhir”. Navoi's views on the power of words as the greatest power, the sanctity of the word, the process of applying the word in practice, and issues of public speaking have been linguistically studied. The ideas are proved by the example of the poet's rubai.

Keywords: oratory, speech culture, communicative qualities of speech, speech accuracy, correctness of speech, imagery.

The work of Alisher Navoi, the sultan of poetry, is a very rich spiritual treasure. This treasure is a building made of the power of words, in every brick of which there is a word, its power, its charm. In almost every work, Navoi dwells on his unique views on words, word power, definition, etiquette, and speech culture. In particular, the twenty-fourth chapter of the poet's work “Makhbub ul-qulub” is entitled “In the remembrance of the people and preachers”, in which the poet expresses his views on the art of preaching, the requirements for a preacher. The gyrus should be a guide to the right path, a bearer of new information to the listener.

Similarly, in “Nazm ul-Javokhir”, the poet expresses his attitude to the power of words, to the art of speech. He considers the word to be a blessing that gives life to the dead and distinguishes man from animals:

By the way, the target is the soul of the dead,

By the way, good news,

Man is a lost animal I know,

There's no better pearl. [1, 2-b]

When we talk about the culture of speech, the rules and requirements of speech, the way to communicate, if the issue is viewed from a linguistic point of view, it is, first of all, the correctness of speech. Secondly, he should be methodically smooth and fluent. Good speech should be against ambiguity, long sentences, clarity and simplicity should be its measure. [3, p. 6] The 160th rubai of the work, “Ayb ul-kalomi tawiyluhu” (Long speech is a defective speech), describes the requirements for speaker during the speech. According to him, the speaker

should be short and to the point, without elaborating, otherwise the sermon may not be acceptable to the audience and may seem flawed:

I can't speak for you

Make it a point to be brief

Someone who finds a lot of guilt in a good word

The limit is too long for seven missing words [1, p. 36].

In the same rubai of the 43rd "Jawdat ul-kalami fil-abbreviation" (the best of the word is short), the poet considers that what makes a speech as disturbing as a flower is its meaning, and that the goodness of this speech lies in its brevity:

Every word is a slogan

The flower of meaning stands in the spring of speech

The word is at the disposal of the nation

The goodness of the word is in the abbreviation [1, p. 17].

Everyone speaks to another person, regardless of social class, and participates directly in such a process, either as a listener or as a speaker. No matter what the subject is, it should be free of harsh words that do not hurt the listener. In verse 116 of the work, the poet dwells on this issue, trying to speak sweetly and avoiding bitter words warns:

Let your speech be a blessing to my nation

Make a covenant with the right not to say a word

Praise your soul for the sake of God

In the quest for Paradise, strive diligently. [1, p. 29]

In some of his rubai, the poet sees the politeness and "sweetness" of the word and urges the preacher to always speak politely. Sweet words make the enemy a friend, pleases the heart, and the harshness of the word hurts the heart:

Everyone, sweet words come to mind

It hurts every month

The harshness of the words hurts the people

Soft-hearted moons. [1, 42-b]

He likens bitter words to poison, saying that bitter food is better than bitter words:

It hurts when someone dies.

It hurts to die with just a few words.

It hurts when so many jokes die.

It's better to be safe than sorry. [1, p. 18]

It is worth noting that Navoi always considers the word power the greatest power. The poet's comments on the subject of the word inevitability, speech activity, the process of applying the word in practice, the issues of eloquence are

relevant not only for his period, but also for the present time, serve for the perfection of human knowledge, educational upbringing.

References:

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